

Wickham's Web: A Case Report Unraveling the Mysteries of Reticular Oral Lichen Planus with Clinical Insights and Literature Synthesis.

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ABSTRACT:

Oral lichen planus (OLP) is a common chronic immunological inflammatory mucocutaneous disorder that varies in appearance from keratotic to erythematous and ulcerative. The estimated prevalence of OLP in the general adult population is 0.5 to 2%. The reported female/male sex ratio is 2:1, and the age of onset is generally between 30 and 60 years. The reticular lesions, the most recognized form of OLP, appear as multiple papules with a network of small, raised, whitish-gray, lacy lesions referred to as Wickham striae. Approximately two-thirds of the patients affected with OLP experience some degree of oral discomfort. This case report, accompanied by a comprehensive literature review, contributes valuable insights to the current understanding of OLP.

KEYWORDS:

Oral lichen planus, Reticular lichen planus, Oral lichenoid reactions, Wickham striae, Oral potentially malignant disorder.

INTRODUCTION:

The term lichen planus (LP) stems from the Greek word “Leichen,” which means “tree moss,” and the Latin word “Planus,” which means “flat,” which describes the surface of the cutaneous lesion¹.

Oral lichen planus (OLP) is a common chronic immunological inflammatory mucocutaneous disorder that varies in appearance from keratotic (reticular or plaque like) to erythematous and ulcerative². Eisen defined OLP as a relatively common chronic inflammatory disorder affecting the stratified squamous epithelia. It is a skin disease common within the oral cavity, where it appears as either white reticular, plaque, or erosive lesions with a prominent T-lymphocyte response in the immediate underlying connective tissue³.

The subtypes of cutaneous LP include, Localized cutaneous lesions of LP, Generalized cutaneous LP, Hypertrophic LP, Palmoplantar LP, Atrophic LP, Actinic LP, Vesiculobullous LP, Annular LP, Erosive and ulcerative LP, LP pigmentosus, Lichen planus pemphigoides, Linear LP, Follicular LP, Papular genital LP, Hypertrophic genital LP, Chronic erosive genital LP.

The subtypes of oral LP include Reticular LP, Papular LP, Plaque-like LP, Bullous LP, Erythematous LP, and Ulcerative LP⁴.

Reticular form is the most common type of oral LP. It appears as a series of fine, radiant, white striae known as Wickham striae, which may be surrounded by a discrete erythematous border. The most common site of involvement is the posterior buccal mucosa, tongue, and gingiva⁵.

The estimated prevalence of OLP in the general adult population is 0.5 to 2%⁶. The incidence of OLP is less well-characterized and displays considerable geographical heterogeneity, ranging between 14 and 250 cases/100,000 persons/year⁷. The reported female/male sex ratio is 2:1, and the age of onset is generally between 30 and 60 years. However, there have been case reports of OLP occurring in children. Genital and cutaneous LP are associated with approximately 20 and 15% of OLP cases, respectively, while it is estimated that OLP occurs in 70 to 77% of patients with cutaneous LP⁸.

Despite extensive research, the exact etiology is still unknown. The most accepted and current data suggest that OLP is a T cell-mediated disorder in which cytokine production leads to apoptosis. Autocytotoxic CD8 and T cells trigger apoptosis of oral epithelial cells. The immune system is triggered due to the interactions among genetic, environmental, and lifestyle factors⁹.

This work aims to present a clinical case of an extensive reticular lichen planus along with its clinical insights, management, and literature synthesis.

CASE PRESENTATION:

History Taking and Clinical Examination:

A 42-year-old female patient reported to the Department of Oral Medicine and Radiology with the chief complaint of burning sensation in right and left buccal mucosa since 1 month. The burning sensation aggravated on consumption of hot and spicy food. There was no history of any relieving factor. There was history of stress since last 4 months. On extraoral examination, no abnormality was detected [Figure 1].

On examination of right buccal mucosa, white striae were seen extending antero-posteriorly (A/P) from mesial of 14 till distal of 18 and supero-inferiorly (S/I) from the line of occlusion of upper molars till upper vestibule. The size was approximately 2.5 cm in diameter. The shape was irregular. The margins were ill-defined and merged with surrounding mucosa. A peripheral erythematous zone was also present. On palpation, all the inspectory findings were confirmed. The white striae were slightly raised, non-scrapable and non-tender [Figure 2].

On examination of left buccal mucosa, white striae were seen extending A/P from distal of 35 to distal of 38 and S/I along the line of occlusion of 36, 37 and 38 involving the attached gingiva and buccal vestibule. The size was approximately 2 cm in diameter. The shape was irregular. The margins were ill-defined and merged with surrounding mucosa. A peripheral erythematous zone was also present. On palpation, all the inspectory findings were confirmed. The white striae were slightly raised, non-scrapable and non-tender [Figure 3].

On hard tissue examination, there was root piece with 36 and tenderness was negative. Pit and fissure caries were seen with 37, 38, 47 and 48. Based on the history and clinical examination, a provisional diagnosis of reticular lichen planus involving right and left buccal mucosa and a differential diagnosis of leukoplakia and lichenoid reaction involving right and left buccal mucosa was given.

Investigations:

The patient was advised to undergo blood investigations like Complete Blood Count (CBC) to rule out any nutritional deficiencies and a significant difference in the cell counts. Further, the CBC findings were unremarkable [Figure 4].

Final Diagnosis:

Based on the above history, clinical examination, and blood investigations, a final diagnosis of reticular lichen planus involving right and left buccal mucosa was given.

Management:**I. Emergency Phase:**

- Ointment Turbocort (0.1% Triamcinolone Acetonide, 0.09 % Methylparaben, 0.01% propylparaben) B.D for 7 days.
- Cap. Lycostar (Lycopene 5 mg, Mixed Carotene 10.33 mg, Zinc Sulphate Monohydrate 27.45 mg, Selenium Dioxide Monohydrate 0.075 mg) T.D.S for 7 days.
- Vitamin C chewable tablet (Limcee 500 mg) B.D for 7 days.

II. Etiotropic Phase:

- Diet Counselling
- Patient Counselling for stress reduction.
- Oral prophylaxis.

III. Restorative Phase:

- Restoration with 37, 38, 47 and 48

IV. Surgical Phase:

- Extraction with 36

V. Maintenance Phase:

- Advised to maintain oral hygiene.
- Recalled after 7 days for follow-up.

Follow Up :

At the 7th day follow-up, there was a significant reduction in the patient's signs and symptoms [Figures 5 and 6].

DISCUSSION:**History of LP:**

Erasmus Wilson first described the condition LP in 1869 as a chronic disease affecting the skin, scalp, nails, and mucosa, with possible malignant transformation. LP may also involve the hair follicles (lichen planopilaris, resulting in scarring alopecia), nails, and, more seldom, the eyes, urinary tract, nasal mucosa, and larynx¹⁰. The oral variant, OLP, is a chronic inflammatory disease affecting the oral mucosa with characteristic relapses and remissions. While cutaneous lesions of LP can be self-limiting and pruritic, oral lesions are commonly chronic, non-remissive, and can be a source of morbidity. OLP may frequently be associated with involvement of the esophagus, and therefore, an endoscopy may be indicated¹¹.

Etiology:

Psychological factors are thought to play a role in the pathogenesis of OLP. OLP patients exhibit higher levels of anxiety, greater depression, and increased vulnerability to psychological disorders, as opposed to healthy controls. Moreover, exacerbations of OLP have been linked to periods of psychological stress and anxiety in some studies. In addition to the chronic discomfort that can result in stress, patients with OLP are shown to be concerned about the possibility of malignancy, the contagious nature of the disease, and the lack of available patient educational materials. The levels of anxiety and salivary cortisol measured in a group of OLP patients were statistically correlated and significantly higher than a control group. Despite the presence of higher levels of psychological stress and anxiety among OLP patients, the question remains whether the psychological factors contribute to the etiology of OLP or are merely driven by the morbidity associated with the condition¹².

Etiopathogenesis:

Possible theories in the etiopathogenesis include the genetic background, where the weak association between HLA antigen and lichen planus was found by Powell et al (1986)¹³. Dental materials and infectious agents like Gram-negative aerobic bacillus, spirochetes, and an increased prevalence of Candida species were suggested by Simon and Hornstein (1980)¹⁴. Vincent et al (1990)¹⁵, Soto Araya et al (2004)¹⁶ reported the strong association of psychological factors like higher levels of stress, anxiety, greater depression, and psychiatric disorders in patients with reticular lichen planus.

Signs and Symptoms:

The clinical signs and symptoms of OLP vary. In many patients, the onset of OLP is insidious, and patients are unaware of their oral condition. Some patients report roughness of the lining of the mouth, burning sensation of the oral mucosa to hot or spicy foods, painful oral mucosa, red or white patches on the oral mucosa, or oral ulcerations. Approximately two-thirds of the patients affected with OLP experience some degree of oral discomfort. OLP has periods of relapses and remissions. During a period of exacerbation, there will be an increase in symptoms and clinical signs, while during periods of quiescence, symptoms and signs of OLP are diminished. Factors such as stress may aggravate the clinical presentation of the disease. Oral post-inflammatory pigmentation has been described in patients with OLP and OLR as diffuse brown or black pigmentation following the lichenoid lesions distribution¹⁷.

Oral Manifestations of Reticular LP:

The reticular lesions, the most recognized form of OLP, appear as multiple papules with a network of small, raised, whitish–gray, lacy lesions referred to as Wickham striae. The striae can also show annular (circular) patterns. The striae often display a peripheral erythematous zone, which reflects a subepithelial inflammation. Although reticular OLP may be encountered in all regions of the oral mucosa, most frequently this form is observed bilaterally in the buccal mucosa and rarely on the mucosal side of the lips. Reticular OLP can sometimes be observed at the vermilion border¹⁸.

Diagnosis:

Clinical criteria for OLP by the World Health Organization (WHO):

1. Presence of bilateral, more or less symmetrical lesions.
2. Presence of a lacelike network of slightly raised gray-white lines (reticular pattern).
3. Erosive, atrophic, bullous, and plaque-type lesions are only accepted as a subtype in the presence of reticular lesions elsewhere in the oral mucosa.
4. In all other lesions that resemble OLP but do not complete the aforementioned criteria, the term “clinically compatible with” should be used.

Histopathologic criteria for OLP by the World Health Organization (WHO):

1. Presence of a well-defined, band-like zone of cellular infiltration that is confined to the superficial part of the connective tissue, consisting mainly of lymphocytes.
2. Signs of liquefaction degeneration in the basal cell layer.
3. Absence of epithelial dysplasia.
4. When the histopathological features are less obvious, the term “histopathologically compatible with” should be used¹⁹.

Malignant potential of OLP:

The first report of a gingival cancer diagnosed in a patient with OLP was in 1910 by Hallapeau. The most important complication of OLP is the development of oral squamous cell carcinoma from the non-keratotic forms. The reported frequency of malignant transformation varies greatly, between 0.4 and over 5%, over periods of observation from 0.5 to over 20 years²⁰.

Management:

1. Topical and systemic steroids -

The most commonly employed and useful agents are topical corticosteroids. Topical corticosteroids reduce pain and inflammation. Triamcinolone acetonide 0.1% in Orabase, oral suspension of triamcinolone, high potency steroid mouthwashes like betamethasone valerate 0.1%, fluocinolone acetonide 0.1%, and clobetasol propionate 0.05% have been used effectively. Systemic corticosteroids should be reserved for recalcitrant erosive or erythematous lichen planus, where the topical approaches have failed, or widespread involvement of skin, genital, esophageal, or scalp involvement.

Daily dosages of 40–80 mg of prednisolone can be used for a brief period, i.e., 5-7 days, and stopping abruptly or the dosage should be reduced by 5-10 mg per day gradually over a 2-4 week period. When using the most potent steroids, the medication is not indicated for more than 15 days. For intractable erosive lesions, intralesional injections of triamcinolone acetonide (10–20 mg/ml per vial) every 2-4 weeks have been found effective, but result in severe pain. Hydrocortisone, methylprednisolone, and dexamethasone can also be tried. One-third of OLP patients who are treated with topical steroids develop secondary candidiasis, which necessitates treatment with antifungals²¹.

2. Immunosuppressive and immunomodulating agents -

Many immunosuppressive agents, like cyclosporine 100 mg/ml, may be used as mouthrinse or finger rub application, and using very low doses of cyclosporine 48 mg/day in an adhesive base was found to be effective in suppressing T cell cytokine production. Treatment of OLP with immunomodulators like levamisole 150 mg per day for 3 days, along with prednisolone, has shown excellent response and long-term remission. Tacrolimus, a steroid-free topical immunosuppressive agent approved for the treatment of atopic dermatitis, is 10-100 times effective than cyclosporine. Topical tacrolimus 0.1% has shown resolution of erosive lesions in 14% of patients as observed by an independent study, but causes a side effect of a burning sensation. The US Food and Drug Administration recently issued a health advisory to inform healthcare providers and patients about a potential cancer risk from the use of tacrolimus. Topical retinoids like isotretinoin gel 0.1%, which act by downregulation of fibroblast function, are of little use when compared with topical steroids²².

3. Other treatment modalities -

Psoralens and long-wave ultraviolet A (PUVA) therapy with 8-methoxy psoralen and photochemotherapy have shown excellent results. To avoid PUVA side effects photosensitizer with topical 0.01% trioxsalen can be used. But the side effects of therapy include oncogenic potential, nausea, vomiting, dizziness, and headache. The psychological factor should also be considered. In highly anxious and depressed patients, psychotherapy should be considered²³.

4. Surgery -

Excision, CO₂ laser, cryosurgery, and photochemotherapy have been effective for persistent or dysplastic lesions. However, surgery may lead to worsening OLP, presumably via a Koebner phenomenon, and reportedly causes a high rate of recurrence²⁴.

Prognosis:

Cutaneous lesions are self-limiting, and pigmentation may fade after a few years or remain permanent. Complete remission occurs in 70% of cases after 1 year. Oral lesions are chronic, rarely undergo spontaneous remission, furthermore, erosive oral lesions are difficult to palliate. The spontaneous remission of OLP is much less than 5% of patients over a 7.5-year follow-up. The reticular form of LP has the best prognosis because spontaneous remission occurs in 40% of cases. The erosive form of the lesion can persist for 15-20 years²⁵.

CONCLUSION:

OLP is a very common oral dermatitis and is one of the most frequent mucosal pathoses encountered by dental practitioners. It is imperative that the lesion is identified precisely and proper treatment be administered at the earliest. It is an immunological disease that requires a thorough evaluation of past medical history, clinical examination including dental status, conclusive histopathological findings, elimination of connected factors, the right treatment protocol, and a regular follow-up. Clinical follow-up of these patients should be carried out in the long term to achieve remission of the lesions, control of the disease, and avoid future complications. This case report, accompanied by a comprehensive literature review, contributes valuable insights to the current understanding of OLP.

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Figure 1: Extraoral profile of the patient.

Figure 2: Wickham striae on right buccal mucosa.

Figure 3: Wickham striae on left buccal mucosa, vestibule and attached gingiva.

Figure 4: CBC report of the patient.

Figure 5: Wickham striae on right buccal mucosa at 7th day follow-up.

Figure 6: Wickham striae on left buccal mucosa at 7th day follow-up.